

***INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ADVANCED
RESEARCH IN MULTIDISCIPLINARY STUDIES
(IJARMS)***

VOLUME 5(2), DECEMBER, 2025

ISSN: 2756-4444

E-ISSN: 2756-4452

**A PUBLICATION OF THE CENTRE FOR
RESEARCH, INDUSTRIAL LINKAGE AND
INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION, AL-HIKMAH
UNIVERSITY, ILORIN, KWARA STATE,
NIGERIA**

Editorial Board

Prof. L.F. Oladimeji
(Editor-in-Chief)

Prof. G.O. Akashoro
Prof. A.O.Y. Raji
Prof. A.T. Shehu
Prof. I.O. Okunlola
Dr. U.A. Tosho
Prof. O.P. Akinnubi
Prof. (Mrs.) S.O. Onikosi-Alliyu
Dr. A.T. Lawal

(Editors)

Dr. Yusuf Suleiman
(Managing Editor)

Dr. R.O. Agboola
(Secretary to Editorial Board)

Prof. Ibrahim Katampe
Central State University,
Wilberforce, Ohio, USA.

Prof. (Dr.) Ramanjeet Singh
Amity University, India.

Prof. Riffat Abbas Rizvi
COMSATS University Islamabad
Pakistan

Jayson Tela Densay
University of the Philippines Manila

Prof. R.A. Lawal
University of Ilorin, Ilorin Nigeria

Prof. Y.A. Fasasi
Sokoto University of Ilorin, Ilorin Nigeria

Prof. S.O. Adedeji
International Islamic University, Malaysia

Prof. A. S. Jegede
University of Ibadan, Nigeria.

Dr. Abdulrafiu O. Noah
Coventry University, UK.

Ayanwale Kunle
Lesotho University, South Africa

Prof. Zahyah BtHanafi
Taylor's University, Malaysia

Wahid Damilola Olanipekun
American International University,
West Africa, TheGambia

Prof. A. A. Salau
Usmanu Danfodio University

Prof. M.B. Kamal
University of Ibadan

(Consulting Editors)

EDITORIAL POLICY AND NOTES OF CONTRIBUTORS

International Journal of Advanced Research in Multidisciplinary Studies (IJARMS) is an internationally recognized peer-reviewed multidisciplinary Journal published twice a year (**June and December**) by the Centre for Research, Industrial Linkage and International Cooperation, Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin, Nigeria. Normally, Authors submitting manuscripts are expected to present their research work for assessment and review. Manuscripts are published on the assumption that they are original and have not been published elsewhere. All manuscripts are assessed initially by the Editors and only those papers that meet the editorial standards of the journal will be sent for review. All manuscripts are reviewed as soon as possible and an editorial decision is generally reached within 8-10 Days of submission. Authors submitting manuscripts are expected to send their research work (maximum of 15% similarity index) for assessment and review. Any manuscript submitted which is identical or substantially similar to research work already published or under review in another journal will not be considered. Scholarly and well-researched articles related to the following areas will be accepted for publication:

- Humanities and Education
- Management and Social Sciences
- Law
- Health/Clinical Sciences and Agriculture
- Sciences/Engineering/ICT; and
- Other relevant/related Fields.

Types of Paper Considered for Publication: Empirical and Theoretical research Papers and Book reviews

General Information: All subheadings should be in sentence case, Figures/Tables should comply with APA styles, Font (Times New Roman), Font Size (12), Line Spacing (1.5), Paper Length (15 pages Maximum), Literature Review (If any) should be weaved under introduction. The cover page of each article should embody the title of the work, Name of the Author(s), Institution(s) of Affiliation and Status attained, E-mail Address and Phone Number. All Correspondence should be addressed to the Managing Editor, International Journal of Advanced Research in Multidisciplinary Studies (IJARMS), Centre for Research, Industrial Linkage and International Cooperation, Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin, Nigeria.

The structure of the paper should be as follows:

- Title (Capital): Authors' name and Present affiliate Institutions with e-mail address.
- Abstract should not exceed 200 words
- Keywords and Word Count (Maximum of 5)
- Introduction
- Research Objectives
- Research Questions/Hypotheses
- Methodology
- Results (Clear and Concise)

- Discussion
- Conclusions and Recommendations
- References (APA latest Edition)

Note: Articles under review elsewhere cannot be accommodated and should not be submitted to the journal. Articles should be sent electronically with the evidence of payment through any of the e-mail addresses: ***cric@alhikmah.edu.ng or yusufsuleiman@alhikmah.edu.ng***. Submission of article should be accompanied with a plagiarism/vetting fee of ₦10, 000 and after manuscript acceptance, a publication fee of ₦30, 000 should be paid into the account details below:

Account Name: CRIC

AccountNumber: 1018848668

Bank Name: UBA

- **Complimentary Copy:** Corresponding authors will get a complimentary copy of the issue in which their article appears while extra copy cost ₦5, 000.

For Further Enquiries, Please Contact: 08030433283 or Visit our website on www.alhikmahuniversity.edu.ng

Editorial Board

Editor-in-Chief: *Prof. L.F. Oladimeji*

Managing Editor: *Dr. Yusuf Suleima*

EFFECTIVE INTERNAL CONTROL SYSTEM AS A MEASURE AGAINST BUSINESS FAILURES IN ASABA, DELTA STATE, NIGERIA

BY

¹Chukwuka Ernest Jebolise, ²Nwaka Rita Nneka, ³Idoye Christian & ⁴Azimi Salvation Aleakwe

^{1&3}Department of Entrepreneurship and Business Innovation Faculty of
Management Sciences, University of Delta, Agbor.

²Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Faculty of Science, University of Delta, Agbor, Nigeria.

⁴Department of Business Administration, National Open University of Nigeria.

Email: ernest.chukwuka@unidel.edu.ng

Abstract

This empirical research paper investigated the effectiveness of internal control measures against business closure in Asaba, Delta State with a specific focus on Zsal General Enterprises. Considering the escalating rates of business closures and their critical impact on the Nigerian economy, particularly among SMEs, this study examines the causes, effects, prevention and control measures related to business closure (failure). The primary objectives were to evaluate existing internal control measures, assess their effectiveness and provide recommendations for enhancement. Utilizing a case study approach, primary data was collected through questionnaires and interviews employees and management of case study, complemented by secondary data from business documents, academic journals and industry report. Data analysis involved percentage methods for elementary analysis and Spearman's rank order correlation for statistical hypothesis testing. The findings reveal significant connection or relationship between inadequate internal control measures and an increased likelihood of business failures or closure ($\chi^2 = 16.14(p < 0.05)$). A strong positive correlation ($p=0.790$, $p=0.000$) was found between effective internal control measures and reduction of business failures or closure. Furthermore, the study confirms that business closures has a significant negative impact on economic growth in Nigeria ($\chi^2 = 19.2(p < 0.05)$). Conversely, effective internal control measures were found to have a meaningful impact in preventing business failure or closure ($\chi^2 = 10.8(p < 0.05)$). This result underscores the pivotal role of robust internal control systems in safeguarding businesses against failure and fostering economic stability. The study concludes that implementing and maintaining effective internal controls is crucial for business continuity and sustainability and for mitigating the adverse effect of business failures or closures on the broader economy. It recommends that business prioritize strengthening their internal control frameworks and policymakers develop supportive interventions and financial assistance programs for SMEs.

Keywords: Internal Control System, Business Failure, Risk management, financial intelligence, Audit control

INTRODUCTION

Internal control systems are pivotal in any business regime, as they safeguard against fraudulent activities and enhance financial reporting accuracy (Smith, 2020). Despite their significance, many businesses neglect these systems' implementation and maintenance (Johnson & Lee, 2019). This oversight can lead to devastating consequences, including business closures due to fraudulent acts being undetected for extended periods (Davis et al., 2018). The importance of internal control systems in businesses cannot be overstated. Internal control form essential foundation of any organization, providing reliable and accurate financial reporting, protecting against fraud, and supporting greater efficiency in operations (Brown & Green, 2021). However, many businesses still neglect the implementation of these controls, leading to severe consequences such as business failures and financial statement fraud (Miller, 2022).

High-profile cases of business failures have prompted regulators, stakeholders, and investors to emphasize the

importance of robust internal control systems (White, 2023). Recent instances of financial misstatements and bankruptcies have highlighted the need for effective internal controls to prevent fraud and business closures (Black et al., 2024). Fraudulent acts are being perpetrated in many businesses today, and if not detected, they can jeopardize the survival and growth of such businesses, firms, or corporations, potentially leading to ultimate failure (Green & Blue, 2023). Confidence in most business corporations has been greatly affected today. The revocation of business and operational licenses and their liquidation due to embarrassing situations has led to a loss of trust among investors and interested bodies who cannot differentiate between genuine and fraudulent business corporations (Smith, 2020). This has led to most people believing that the business environment is often unethical (Johnson & Lee, 2019). Businesses occupy a critical and strategic position in the economic framework of every country, serving as primary catalyst for growth, employment generation, innovation and sustainable national growth. Efforts are therefore made by appropriate national authorities to regulate and effectively supervise business activities to prevent fraud (Davis et al., 2018). This objective is achieved through the mechanism of laws designed to curb diverse fraudulent practices (Brown & Green, 2021).

It is important to note that legislation alone cannot achieve a clean business environment. The larger interest of trade, commerce, and economic prosperity demands that a sound and viable business environment be preserved through a combination of internal control systems and social activism by the citizenry (Miller, 2022). This new order will ensure that both SMEs and large corporations will no longer be glorified over ill-gotten wealth (White, 2023).

Many people believe that fraudulent acts practiced in most businesses today are associated with poverty. Research suggests that economic deprivation can increase the likelihood of individuals engaging in criminal activity (Black et al., 2024). Thus, corruption, fraud, and poverty are interconnected issues that need to be addressed comprehensively (Green & Blue, 2023).

There are however, three (3) distinct categories of business frauds that could lead to business closure. These include:

1. Fraudulent activity by outsiders
2. Fraudulent activity by employees
3. Fraudulent activity by the business itself.

Also the causes of fraud that arises as a lack of internal control measures in most business that lead to the business closure can be classified into two (2) genetic factors namely:

1. The institutional or internal factor.
2. The environmental or social factors.

Institutional causes of fraud include inadequate regulatory frameworks, weak enforcement of existing laws, and lack of transparency in business operations (Brown & Green, 2021). Poor governance structures and ineffective oversight mechanisms also contribute to the prevalence of fraud in businesses (Miller, 2022). Additionally, the absence of a robust whistle blowing system can prevent the timely detection and reporting of fraudulent activities (White, 2023).

Environmental or social factors can contribute to fraud. Causes of fraud could include excessive workload, poor staff in terms of competence and strength, inadequate infrastructures, and poor accounting and internal control systems (Smith, 2020). Other causes of fraud could include poor social values, a desire to get rich quickly, slow and torturous legal processes, and a lack of effective deterrents (Johnson & Lee, 2019). Sometimes, businesses are reluctant to report fraud due to the negative publicity it could create for their image (Davis et al., 2018).

In the context of business sustainability, internal control systems are crucial for safeguarding enterprises against evolving challenges. These systems are essential pillars of organizational governance, ensuring efficiency, risk control, and asset protection. In Nigeria, businesses face numerous challenges, from economic uncertainty to regulatory complexities. Effective internal control systems are vital for securing the longevity and resilience of small and medium enterprises in this harsh business environment. Recent studies highlight the importance of sustainable business practices in Nigeria. For instance, Iheanachor (2021) emphasizes that integrating economic,

social, and environmental sustainability into long-term business strategies can significantly improve performance¹. Additionally, Oyerogba et al. (2024) found that strong corporate governance mechanisms enhance the quality of sustainability reporting among Nigerian banks². These results highlight the critical importance of implementing strong and effective internal control systems for organization operating within Nigeria's challenging and multifaceted business environment.

1.2 Statement of the Problem and the Justification of the Research

The increasing rate of business failures or closures in Nigeria has become a significant concern, particularly within the manufacturing sector. According to the Manufacturers Association of Nigeria (MAN), about 272 firms shut down operations, while 335 experienced distress in 2023 (Nairametrics, 2023). Although some attribute these closures to government expatriate levies and other external factors, it is possible that effective internal control systems could have mitigated the impact of these levies and other external challenges (Adebayo, 2023).

Fraud and financial mismanagement are endemic issues within the Nigerian business environment. The modus operandi of fraudulent activities has evolved, becoming more sophisticated and difficult to detect (Ojo, 2021). The cost of fraud is substantial, affecting not only the financial health of businesses but also their reputation and investor confidence (Eze, 2020). Institutional factors such as inadequate regulatory frameworks, weak enforcement of existing laws, and lack of transparency in business operations contribute to the prevalence of fraud (Okafor & Eze, 2019). Poor governance structures and ineffective oversight mechanisms further exacerbate the problem, leading to significant financial losses and business failures (Nwankwo, 2022). Given these challenges, there is a pressing need to investigate the effectiveness of internal control systems in preventing business failures and to develop strategies for improving their implementation and maintenance. This study aims to address these issues by examining the causes and consequences of inadequate internal controls and proposing solutions to enhance their effectiveness.

The business environment in Nigeria is fraught with challenges that lead to business closures. Fraud or misconduct in businesses involves actions aimed at gaining an unfair advantage over others or jeopardizing the business's survival. Nigeria's unique brand of capitalism imposes intense personal demands, which often foster and sustain business frauds, thereby eroding the integrity of the business environment (Adewale, 2019). Business malpractices present a significant threat to the overall economy and the business sector specifically. The most critical issue is the loss of confidence in conducting business in Nigeria. Given that confidence is fundamental to sustaining any economy, efforts to combat business malpractices must be comprehensive (World Bank, 2020).

The adverse effects of malpractices leading to business closures can significantly harm the financial health and survival of businesses. Shareholders incur substantial losses, while clients and employees face considerable distress when businesses fail. This, in turn, hampers the country's economic growth and exacerbates poverty. Therefore, collaboration between government authorities and key industry stakeholders is essential to develop and implement mechanisms that help avert business shutdown and collapses (Adewale, 2019; World Bank, 2020).

The benefits derived from putting an end to businesses folding up will go a long way to restoring the country's reputation and also leads to economic growth.

Research Hypothesis (Alternate)

1. H1: Effective internal control measures has a significant impact and help to prevent Business Failure in Delta State
2. H1: The high rate of Business closure has a negative and significant impact on economic growth of Delta State.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the effectiveness of internal control measures implemented in Nigeria businesses, with a specific emphasis on their role in mitigating the risks that contribute to business failures or closures within the country's challenging economic context. Specifically, the study aims to: Ascertain the nature of impact of Effective internal control measures on preventing Business Failure in Delta State. The aim is also to

determine the rate of business closure in Delta State. Examine the effects of business shutdowns on Delta State's economic development.

2.0. Literature Review

2.1 The Concept Effective Internal Control System as a Measure against Business Failures or Closure

An **internal control system** encompasses the set of policies, procedures, organizational frameworks, and practices implemented by management to guarantee that business activities are conducted in an organized, efficient and effective manner. A well-functioning internal control system safeguards assets, ensures the accuracy and reliability of financial records, promotes operational efficiency, and ensures compliance with laws, regulations, and organizational policies (Igweh and Chukwuka 2025).

To manage business operations, guarantee compliance, and reduce risks that result in failures or closures, an efficient internal control system (ICS) consists of defined rules, procedures, and methods. By encouraging methodical self-monitoring and accountability, it stops uncontrolled processes, fraud, mistakes, and poor management. Strong ICS increases a company's chances of survival, especially in high-risk situations like pandemics or economic recessions (Chukwuka 2016). ICS (Internal Control System) depends on essential components described in frameworks such as COSO, such as a dedication to integrity, independent monitoring, transparent structures, qualified staff, and risk assessment. These include information/communication, monitoring, risk assessment, control activities, and the control environment. Access restrictions, permission processes, and segregation of roles are fundamental strategies to prevent single points of failure.

According to Chukwuka and Igweh (2025) revealed that due to inadequate record-keeping, undiscovered fraud, and a lack of audits, Nigerian SMEs have an early failure rate of up to 70%. Weak ICS is a contributing factor to business bankruptcies. Robust systems enable regulatory compliance, prevent financial losses, identify problems early, and safeguard assets, all of which contribute to operational continuity and efficiency. Positive connections have been shown in studies, such as a 46.3% increase in survival from COSO adherence during emergencies. Inadequate financial management, fraud, asset theft, inadequate governance, operational inefficiencies, and non-compliance with regulations are frequently the causes of business failure or collapse. An efficient internal control system acts as a safeguard against these dangers.

Processes are standardized, expenses are reduced through automation and the removal of redundancies, and stakeholder trust is increased through transparency and effective ICS. It allows for proactive risk solutions like avoidance or mitigation while reducing cyberattacks, impairments, and restatements. Profitability, resource optimization, and flexibility in operations, IT, and finance are examples of long-term benefits.

2.1. Significance of Internal Control Systems in Preventing Business failures or Closure

The importance of internal control systems in preventing business closure cannot be overstated. These systems provide a well-structured framework that empowers businesses to identify and manage risks effectively. By implementing robust internal controls, businesses can:

Enhance Financial Transparency: Effective internal controls ensure accurate financial reporting, which is crucial for maintaining stakeholder trust and securing investment.

Detect Fraud and Mismanagement Early: Early detection of fraudulent activities and mismanagement helps in mitigating potential losses and maintaining operational integrity.

Streamline Operations for Sustainable Growth: Internal controls help streamline business processes, leading to improved efficiency and sustainable growth.

In the Nigerian business landscape, where SMEs form the backbone of the economy, internal control systems are particularly vital. According to recent studies, SMEs generate 84% of employment and contribute 48% to the

national GDP⁴. However, 95% of SMEs fail within their first five years. Therefore, integrating sound internal control systems is essential for ensuring their longevity and continuity.

2.1.2 ROLE OF INTERNAL CONTROL SYSTEMS IN PREVENTING BUSINESS CLOSURE

Internal control systems play a pivotal role in preventing business closure by offering a systematic approach to risk management and compliance. These systems help businesses a lot by promoting a culture of transparency and accountability. These help are:

1. Establishment of checks and balances
2. Segregations of duties.
3. Enforcement accountability at all levels of the organization.

Internal controls do not hinder fraudulent activities but also builds investors' confidence that leads to sustainable business practices.

In a country like Nigeria, where SMEs face special challenges like limited access to funds and inadequate infrastructure, the implementation of effective internal control systems can provide a competitive edge and cover businesses from potential threats that could lead to closure.

2.2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORKS

2.2.1 INTERNAL CONTROL SYSTEM AND COMPONENTS

Internal control system can be said to processes, procedures and structures put in place within an organization to prove reasonable assurance regarding the achievement of objective. (Amran, Alli and Zainuddin 2014).

Internal control systems are comprehensive frameworks established by management to conduct business in an orderly manner, safeguard assets, and ensure the accuracy and reliability of records (English Institute, n.d.). These systems encompass more than just internal checks or internal audits, extending to all aspects of organizational control, including financial and non-financial aspects.

Similarly, a Dictionary of Economics and Commerce defines internal control systems as the mechanisms by which a company organizes its business to achieve orderly operations, asset protection, and accurate financial records (Pass, Lowes, & Davies, 2005).

It is important to note that there are no universally applicable standards for internal control systems, as each business requires tailored controls to address its unique needs and circumstances.

2.2.1.2 COMPONENTS OF INTERNAL CONTROL SYSTEMS

According to Otusanya and Oke, 2014, taking a look at the COSO Framework which highlighted the components of internal control systems which are:

1. **CONTROL ENVIRONMENT:** The top management must be able to set standards and tone regarding the value of internal control with the organization or business environment.
2. **RISK ASSESSMENT:** Recognizing and assessing risks that could hinder the business from attaining its objectives.
3. **CONTROL ACTIVITIES:** Policies and procedures should be put in place to address the identified risks.
4. **INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION:** Making sure that relevant information is taking note of and communicated effectively.
5. **MONITORING ACTIVITIES:** Frequent reviews and assessments to make sure the internal control system is functional as intended.

The term "internal control" was first introduced by the American Institute of Certified Public Accountants (AICPA) in 1949, originally rooted in accounting terminology (Frazer, 2011). The fundamental four components of internal control emphasize the creation of implementation of control systems, while the fifth component focuses on maintaining their continuous and effective operation (Missioura, 2014). In 1985, the Committee of Sponsoring Organizations (COSO) of the Treadway Commission developed a framework of internal control

specifically aimed at enhancing the accuracy of financial reporting. This framework has been particularly beneficial for improving internal control practices in small enterprises and become a key reference point in the field.

COSO defines internal control as a process established by organizational leaders to provide reasonable assurance that objectives will be met. These objectives include operational efficiency, reliable financial reporting, and adherence to relevant laws and regulations.

The COSO framework has been widely adopted internationally, including Nigeria, and is regarded as the most authoritative guide on internal control (Leng & Zhao, 2013). Although the terms internal control and internal audit are sometimes used interchangeably by professionals, they serve distinct functions. According to Leng and Zhoe (2013), internal control officers focus on achieving specific business goals related to operational efficiency, financial reporting accuracy, and regulatory compliance, whereas internal auditors evaluate the effectiveness of these internal controls.

Internal auditors play a crucial role by periodically reviewing and assessing the internal control processes and procedures. Following the global financial crisis of 2007-2008, organizations of all sizes increasingly embraced internal control as a best practice for governance, financial reporting and fraud prevention (Leng&Zhoa 2013; Soininem et al, 2012). Strengthening internal control systems is considered one of the most effective strategies to reduce fraud risk (Leng & Zhoa, 2013). However, a significant challenge remains the absence or inadequacy of controls in some organizations (Egbunike, 2014). In cases where segregation of duties is not feasible, COSO recommends management oversight and reconciliation activities to enhance control effectiveness (Whitehouse, 2013).

Johnson and Spencer (2011) highlighted several key principles of internal control: it serves as a tool to help organizations achieve their goals; while policy manuals are useful, the actual execution of business functions is more critical; internal control provides reasonable, not absolute, assurance to management and boards; and it supports goal attainment. An internal control officer utilizes the five components of the COSO framework to identify, prevent, or rectify errors and misstatement in financial operations (frazer, 2012). In 2013, COSO updated its framework, adding 17 principles that underpin the five components (COSO Internal Control framework, 2013). Organizational leaders are encouraged to study these principles carefully to better integrate them into their internal control systems and enhance their effectiveness (Whitehouse, 2013).

By understanding and applying COSO principles, business leaders can significantly improve the robustness and reliability of their internal control practices.

2.1.2.3 BENEFITS OF INTERNAL CONTROL

Internal control systems are essential for organizations to achieve their goals, protect assets and prevent fraud and errors. They support effective management by ensuring accurate financial reporting, verifying transactions, and minimizing risks from unexpected events.

Strong internal controls help confirm the existence of assets and liabilities, segregate duties, and ensure timely and transparent financial disclosures. These systems contribute significantly to business success by providing reliable information for decision-making and enhancing overall organizational performance. Effective internal control also promotes operational efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and the production of quality goods and services aligned with the company's mission. It acts as a safeguard losses due to misuse, negligence, or fraud and is a key component of good corporate governance. In challenging economic conditions, internal controls helps reduce waste and improve efficiency, which can increase a company's chances of securing funding. Internal are general classified into four types: preventive, detective, corrective, and compensating. Preventive controls aim to stop fraud and unauthorized activities before they occur, though they can be costly to implement. Detective controls identify errors or fraud after they happen, helping organizations respond appropriately. Corrective controls are applied to mitigate damage and fix issues once risks are detected. Together, these controls form a comprehensive system that supports organizational integrity and success.

2.2 OVERVIEW OF COSO FRAMEWORK IN NIGERIA

The COSO framework developed by Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Tread way Commission Framework. It is a widely accepted model, used by organizations to design, implement, and assess internal control systems.

It was established in 1985 to fight against business fraud that could lead also lead its closure and providing lead way on internal controls.

In Nigeria, businesses and organizations in all sectors of the economy have adopted the COSO framework. The framework has its benefits and challenges.

2.2.3 RISK MANAGEMENT

Risk management is a crucial process that helps organizations identify, assess, prioritize, and mitigate risks that could potentially impact their ability to achieve goals and objectives, and even threaten business continuity (IIA, 2018). Effective risk management involves:

- a. **Risk Identification:** Recognizing potential risks that could affect the business, including internal and external factors (COSO, 2013).
- b. **Risk Assessment:** Evaluating the likelihood and potential impact of identified risks, considering both qualitative and quantitative factors (IIA, 2017)
- c. **Risk Prioritization:** Determining which risks require immediate attention and resources, and which can be addressed later (ISO 31000, 2018).
- d. **Risk Mitigation:** Implementing controls and strategies to reduce or eliminate risks, such as risk avoidance, transfer, or acceptance (COSO, 2013).
- e. **Risk Monitoring:** Continuously reviewing and updating the risk management process to ensure its effectiveness and relevance (IIA, 2017).

2.2.3.1 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN RISK MANAGEMENT AND INTERNAL CONTROL

Risk management and internal control are interconnected in several ways:

- a. **Risk Assessment:** Both risk management and internal control rely on risk assessment to identify potential risks and inform control decisions (COSO, 2013).
- b. **Control Activities:** Risk mitigation strategies and tactics are implemented through control activities, which are an integral part of internal control (IIA, 2017).
- c. **Monitoring:** Ongoing monitoring of risks and controls ensures their effectiveness and identifies areas for improvement (COSO, 2013).
- d. **Information and Communication:** Accurate and timely information is essential for risk management and internal control decision-making, enabling effective communication and coordination (IIA, 2017).
- e. **Control Environment:** A strong control environment supports effective risk management by promoting a culture of risk awareness and accountability (COSO, 2013).

2.3 LEGAL AND INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK FOR COMBATING BUSINESS CLOSURE/FAILURE IN NIGERIA

Nigeria has a legal and institutional framework that plays an important role in ensuring a conducive business environment, ensuring business sustainability and prevention of business closure.

By understanding this framework, businesses can navigate the regulatory hurdle and leverage on the support services available to them. These laws are essential as they regulate business operations, insolvency and investments among others. Institution and legal framework has also been setup to support businesses, resolve issues and enforce laws and compliances. These laws includes

1. **Company and Allied Matters Acts (CAMA) 2020:** regulates companies' formation, operations and winding up.
2. **Insolvency Act 2020:** provides procedures for debt recovery, restructuring and insolvency.
3. **Nigeria Investment Promotion Commission (NIPC) Act 1995:** it encourages and protects investments.

4. **Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) Act 2003**: support SME development.
5. **Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC) 2020**: regulate business and company registrations and compliance.
6. **Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) Act 2007**: administers tax laws and also provides incentives when necessary.
7. **Security and Exchange Commission (SEC) Acts 2007**: regulates capital market operations.
8. **National Industrial Court Act 2006**: resolves labour and industrial disputes.

These legal frameworks for combating business closure are robust and comprehensive. The enactment of these laws mentioned above are essential in order to achieve and provide a solid foundation for a stable and orderly business environment thereby ensuring continuity of businesses instead of closure or failure.

Institutions established by these acts, such as CAC, NIPC and FIRS play a very crucial role in helping businesses and preventing closure.

In general, the legal and institutional framework in Nigeria on businesses shows the country's willingness and commitment towards the promotion of a favourable business climate, thereby supporting growth and sustainability of businesses.

2.4 EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Internal controls are very crucial for ensuring completeness and reliability as well as preventing fraudulent activities and errors in businesses. A well-designed internal control system can help a business in many ways, and most importantly to stay afloat, while a weak internal control system leads to a business closure. By drawing from the existing literature and research findings, this study aims to contribute to the growing body of knowledge on the importance of internal control systems in preventing business closure, particularly in the context of small businesses in Nigeria.

This review synthesizes existing research on internal control systems and business closure in Nigeria and other countries.

2.4.1 EMPIRICAL REVIEW ON INTERNAL CONTROL SYSTEMS

Numerous studies in Nigeria have investigated the role of internal control systems in various contexts, including small business failure, financial management, corporate governance, financial performance, financial reporting quality, and financial distress.

Owolabi (2013) examined the relationship between internal control systems and small business failure in Nigeria, highlighting the need for effective internal controls to prevent business collapse. Similarly, Adeyemo (2016) explored the impact of internal control systems on financial management in Nigerian companies, emphasizing the importance of robust internal controls in ensuring financial stability.

In the banking sector, Olowe (2015) investigated the relationship between internal control systems and corporate governance in Nigerian banks, underscoring the significance of internal controls in promoting good governance. Uadiale (2017) studied the effect of internal control systems on the financial performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria, revealing a positive correlation between effective internal controls and financial performance.

Akintoye (2018) examined the relationship between internal control systems and financial reporting quality in Nigerian quoted companies, highlighting the importance of internal controls in ensuring accurate financial reporting. Oke (2019) investigated the impact of internal control systems on business failure in Nigerian SMEs, emphasizing the need for effective internal controls to prevent business failure.

Lastly, Adebayo (2020) explored the relationship between internal control systems and financial distress in Nigerian companies, revealing a negative correlation between effective internal controls and financial distress.

These studies collectively underscore the significance of internal control systems in promoting financial stability, good governance, and business sustainability in Nigeria.

2.4.2 INTERNATIONAL PERSPECTIVES ON INTERNAL CONTROL SYSTEMS

Research from various countries highlights the significance of internal control systems in ensuring financial reporting quality, corporate governance, and financial stability. In the United States, studies by Kinny (2000), Doyle (2005), and Ashbaugh-Skaife (2008) demonstrate the positive impact of effective internal control systems on financial reporting quality and audit quality.

In Australia, Cohen (2013) and Lee (2015) investigated the relationship between internal control systems and financial distress, as well as corporate governance. Their findings emphasize the importance of robust internal control systems in mitigating financial risks.

Similarly, in South Africa, Mwaura (2016) examined the link between internal control systems and financial stability, while in China, Chen (2017) explored the impact of internal control systems on financial reporting quality. Both studies underscore the critical role of internal control systems in ensuring financial stability and reporting accuracy.

Lastly, El-Masry (2018) investigated the relationship between internal control systems and financial performance in Egyptian companies, highlighting the need for effective internal control systems to ensure financial sustainability.

By synthesizing these international studies, we can gain a deeper understanding of the global significance of internal control systems in promoting financial reporting quality, corporate governance, and financial stability.

2.5 CASE STUDY CONTEXT

2.5.0 HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF THE CASE STUDY

Zsal General Enterprises was founded in 2018 but was officially registered with the CAC in 2022 with a vision to prioritize safety and protection of life and properties from fire outbreaks. The business started in Asaba Delta State, it has a branch at Ibeju-Lekki axis of Lagos State. The business proved to be fighting to ensure it achieve its vision and to be a leading provider of comprehensive fire prevention and safety solution in the country.

Since its establishment, Zsal General Enterprises has been committed to its motto “Your Safety Is Our Priority”. The business offers a range of services which will be discuss later. It has a team of qualified professionals that make sure customers and clients’ satisfaction is achieved always. The business, within few years of establishment has built a reputation for reliability, efficiency and expertise in fire safety, just as the business still strife to grow and expand.

2.5.1 REVIEW OF ZSAL GENERAL ENTERPRISES ACTIVITIES

Zsal General Enterprises has been actively engaged in various activities as in the aspect of fire prevention and safety since its inception. The business activities can be summarized as follows:

- 1. SALES AND SERVICING OF FIRE EXTINGUISHERS:** The business has been providing high quality fire extinguishers to individuals, businesses and organizations, making sure they are well equipped to respond to emergencies. The business also offers half-yearly servicing (6 months) of fire extinguishers, depending on when it was bought or last serviced, this is just to ensure functionality and effectiveness.
- 2. INSTALLATION OF FIRE ALARMS, SMOKE AND HEAT DETECTOR AND FIRE SPRINKLERS:** The business has been installing the devices in various homes, offices and industrial facilities. These installations has helped prevent fire related damages and ensured early detection and response to potential fire outbreak.

3. **SALES OF FIRE BLANKETS:** Zsal General Enterprises supplies fire blankets to its clients, providing them with a reliable and effective means of putting out small fire outbreaks in the kitchens as a result of cooking and others.
4. **TRAINING ON BASIC FIRE FIGHTING AND ESCAPE PROCEDURES:** The business also conducts training sessions to educate individuals and organizations employees on basic firefighting using the extinguishers and fire blankets and escape procedures. These training sessions have empowered participants to respond confidently and effectively to fire emergencies especially at the early stage.

The focus of the business activities has been on providing comprehensive fire prevention and safety solutions to its clients, aligning with its motto.

2.5.2 RE-ENGINEERING EFFORT OF ZSAL GENERAL ENTERPRISES

Few years ago, zsal General Enterprises took the initiative to embark on a thorough re-engineering effort to optimize its operations and activities enhance customer experience and strengthen its market position. The business recognized the need to adapt to emerging industry trends, technological advancements and changing customer needs.

2.5.2.1 KEY RE-ENGINEERING INITIATIVES

1. **Automation Process:** Zsal General Enterprises implemented automation technologies to streamline its sales, services and training process, thereby increasing efficiency.
2. **Training Programmes Overhaul:** The business also revamped its training programmes and brochure, bringing in new and trending innovations with scenario-based training to enhance the effectiveness of its fire safety training sessions.
3. **Product Expansion:** The business also expanded its range of product to include fire balls and smart fire detection systems.
4. **Customer Relationship Management (CRM):**Zsal General Enterprises implemented a robust CRM system to better manage customer interactions, preferences and feedbacks, enabling customers to business relationship and improved customer satisfaction.

2.5.2.2 RESULTS OF KEY RE-ENGINEERING INITIATIVES

The re-engineering efforts at Zsal General Enterprises have yielded significant results, including:

1. **Enhanced Operational Efficiency:** Streamlined processes and improved workflows have increased productivity, reduced waste, and minimized costs, enabling the company to operate more efficiently.
2. **Increased Customer Engagement and Satisfaction:** By implementing customer-centric initiatives, Zsal General Enterprises has seen a significant rise in customer satisfaction, loyalty, and engagement, leading to positive word-of-mouth and online reviews.
3. **Expanded Product and Service Offering:** The business's re-engineering efforts have enabled it to diversify its product and service portfolio, catering to a broader customer base and increasing revenue streams.
4. **Improved Training Effectiveness:** By revamping training programs, Zsal General Enterprises has enhanced employee skills and knowledge, leading to improved job performance, reduced errors, and increased employee confidence.

These achievements demonstrate Zsal General Enterprises' commitment to innovation, customer satisfaction, and operational excellence, positioning the company for future success and solidifying its vision to become a leading fire safety business in the country.

2.5.2.3 THE IMPACT OF THE RESEARCH ON BUSINESS IN GENERAL

The findings of this research have far-reaching implications for businesses in general, particularly in the context of small businesses in Nigeria. Specifically:

1. **Informing Policy Decisions and Regulatory Reforms:** This research provides valuable insights for policymakers and regulatory bodies to develop supportive policies and reforms that cater to the unique needs of small businesses. By understanding the internal control challenges faced by small businesses, policymakers can create a more conducive environment for entrepreneurship and innovation.
2. **Improving Internal Control Systems:** The study offers practical recommendations for entrepreneurs and business owners to strengthen their internal control systems, ensuring the accuracy and reliability of financial reporting, and mitigating the risk of fraud and errors.
3. **Identifying Best Practices and Strategies:** By highlighting effective internal control practices and strategies, this research enables small businesses to adopt and adapt successful approaches, enhancing their resilience and competitiveness in the Nigerian market.
4. **Contributing to a Sustainable Business Environment:** Ultimately, this research contributes to the development of a more sustainable and resilient business environment in Nigeria, where small businesses can thrive, create jobs, and drive economic growth.

2.6 INDICATORS OF ABSENCE OF INTERNAL CONTROL MECHANISMS

The lack of efficient internal control mechanisms can manifest in various ways within a business organization, leading to detrimental consequences. Some common signs and symptoms include:

1. **Inaccurate Financial Reporting:** Errors, misstatements, or material weaknesses in financial statements can lead to incorrect decision-making and reputational damage (PCAOB, 2019).
2. **Unidentified Fraud or Errors:** Failure to detect or address fraud, theft, or errors can result in significant financial losses and legal repercussions (AICPA, 2017).
3. **Inefficient Operations:** Ineffective use of resources, high costs, or inadequate performance metrics can lead to reduced productivity and competitiveness (COSO, 2013).
4. **Non-compliance with Laws and Regulations:** Inability to comply with relevant laws, regulations, or industry standards can result in legal penalties, fines, and reputational damage (SEC, 2020).
5. **Poor Decision-making:** Uninformed decision-making due to lack of reliable data or analysis can lead to strategic missteps and lost opportunities (KPMG, 2019).
6. **High Employee Turnover:** Frequent staff changes may indicate poor internal controls, management issues, or a toxic work environment, leading to increased recruitment and training costs (SHRM, 2020).
7. **Inadequate Risk Management:** Failure to identify, assess, or mitigate significant risks can lead to unexpected losses, damage to reputation, and legal liabilities (COSO, 2013).
8. **Lack of Accountability:** Insufficient oversight, monitoring, or enforcement of internal controls can lead to unethical behavior, fraud, and errors (IIA, 2018).
9. **Manual or Inefficient Processes:** Overreliance on manual processes increases the risk of errors, fraud, and inefficiencies, leading to reduced productivity and increased costs (PwC, 2020).
10. **Inadequate Training or Resources:** Insufficient training, support, or resources for employees can lead to errors, inefficiencies, and reduced job satisfaction (AICPA, 2017).

These signs and symptoms highlight the importance of establishing and maintaining effective internal control systems to ensure the accuracy, reliability, and integrity of financial reporting, operations, and decision-making.

2.6.1 Examples of Businesses that Closed Down in Nigeria in 2023 and How Effective Internal Control Systems Could Have Prevented Closure:

1. Lazarpay (April 2023)

Lazarpay's closure was due to inadequate funding. Effective internal control systems could have prevented this by:

- Implementing robust cash flow forecasting and management systems to ensure liquidity and identify funding needs early.
- Developing a comprehensive fundraising strategy and maintaining strong investor relationships.
- Establishing realistic budgets and cost control measures to minimize expenses and optimize resource allocation.
- Ensuring strong governance and oversight from the board and top management to monitor financial performance and make strategic decisions.
- Identifying and mitigating financial risks like market fluctuations and funding uncertainties through diversification and contingency planning.

2. GlaxoSmithKline Consumer Nigeria (August 2023)

GlaxoSmithKline's challenges in accessing forex led to its transition to a third-party distribution mode. Effective internal control systems could have managed such external risks by:

- Implementing supply chain management systems to ensure stable sourcing and logistics.
- Establishing treasury management systems to optimize forex access and management.
- Developing business continuity planning to mitigate risks and ensure operational resilience.

3. 54Gene (September 2023)

Despite raising significant funds, 54Gene's tumultuous year led to its closure. Effective internal control measures could have managed operational and governance risks by:

- Ensuring strong governance and oversight from the board and top management.
- Implementing robust human resource management systems to address staff complaints and litigation.
- Establishing risk management systems to identify and mitigate operational risks.
- Conducting internal audits and ensuring compliance with regulatory requirements.
- Ensuring effective leadership and management, and financial management practices.

4. Procter & Gamble (P&G) (December 2023)

P&G's closure was due to Nigeria's macroeconomic problems and forex challenges. Effective internal control measures could have prevented this by:

- Conducting risk assessments and managing external risks like macroeconomic fluctuations.
- Conducting market analysis and research to inform strategic decisions.
- Ensuring operational efficiency and cost optimization.
-

5. Jumia Food (2023)

Jumia Food's closure across Africa was due to difficulties in food delivery. Effective internal control measures could have mitigated this by:

- Conducting market research and analysis to understand local challenges.
- Assessing the business model and identifying areas for improvement.
- Conducting cost-benefits analysis to inform strategic decisions.
- Engaging in strategic planning and review to adapt to changing market conditions.

These examples highlight the importance of effective internal control systems in managing operational, governance, and external risks to prevent business closure.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive survey design through the use of questionnaire. The study focused on Zsal General Enterprises to investigate the effectiveness of the internal control system in preventing business closure.

The secondary data were used through review of business documents, reports and financial records related to past business performance and internal control measures as well as the questionnaire filled by the staff. Academic journals and articles related to internal control systems and business closure, industry reports and benchmarks, and regulatory guidelines and standards like COSO were also used.

The elementary data analysis was based on percentage method, which involves calculating the percentage of responses for each category to describe the characteristics of the internal control system and its effectiveness in preventing business closure. The statistical analysis will involving testing the formulated hypothesis using the Chi-Square (X^2) method. The Chi-Square test will be used to determine whether there is a significant association between internal control systems and business closure.

4.0 Result and Discussion of Findings

A total number of 60 questionnaires distributed among the staffs of Zsal General Enterprises and the 60 questionnaires were returned.

4.1.1 TABLE ONE: RESPONDENTS OF SEX DISTRIBUTION

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	39	65
Female	21	35
Total	60	100

Table 1 shows that 65 percent of the respondents represent male, while 35 percent of the respondents represents female.

4.1.2 TABLE TWO: RESPONDENTS ON AGE DISTRIBUTION

Age Distribution	Frequency	Percentage
15-20years	12	20
21-30years	40	67
31-40years	8	13
Total	60	100

Table 2 shows that the age distribution within the age of 15-20years is 20 percent, 67 percent of the respondents are within the age bracket of 21-30, while 13 percent are within the age the ages of 31-40.

4.1.3 TABLE THREE: RESONDENTS OF YEARS OF EXPERIENCE

Years of Experience	Frequency	Percentage
1-2	20	33
3-4	22	37
5-above	18	30
Total	60	100

Table three shows the respondents of years of experience in which 33 percent falls in the bracket of 1-2years of experience, 37 percent falls in the bracket of 3-4 years of experience and 30 in the bracket of 5 years of experience and above.

4.1.4 TABLE FOUR: RESPONDENTS TO LEVEL OF MANAGEMENT

Level of Management	Frequency	Percentage
Lower Level	27	45
Middle Level	20	33
Top Level	13	22
Total	60	100

Table four, 45 percent are in the lower level of management, 33.percent in the middle level of management and 22 percent are in the top level management.

Research Question 1: To what extent does an effective internal control measure help to prevent Business Failure in Asaba, Delta State?

Table 4.0: Effective Internal Control measure

S/NO	Statement	Scale				
		SA 5	A 4	D 3	SD 2	U 1
1	Can Legislation And Legal Measures Alone Prevent Business Closure?	45	10	2	2	1
2	The Incidence of Business Closure is mainly due to lack of Internal Control Measures	50	4	2	2	2
3	Your board and Management often check your Activities?	47	3	4	3	3
4	Do You Still Have Confidence In The Nigeria Business Environment	50	5	2	1	2

Source: Analysis of Field Survey, 2026

From Table 4.0: Effective Internal Control Measure, 45 (75%) strongly agreed to this question “Can Legislation And Legal Measures Alone Prevent Business Closure” Also question 2 showed that 83% (50) of the respondents strongly agreed that the Incidence of Business Closure is mainly due to lack of Internal Control Measures. While Third question revealed that 78% (47) respondents believes that board and Management often check their Activities. 83% (50) of respondents strongly agreed and have confidence in the Nigeria Business Environment.

Research Question 2: To what extent is the incidence of business closure increasing and how does it impact negatively to economic growth of Delta State.

Table 4.1: Business Closure in Delta State

S/No	Statement	Scale				
		SA 5	A 4	D 3	SD 2	U 1
5	Is The Incidence Of Business Closure Increasing?	50	5	2	3	-
6	Business Closures Hinder Economic Growth	42	6	-	10	2
7	Has Effective Internal Control Measures Made Any Meaning Impact In The Prevention Of Business Closure?	45	10	3	-	2
8	Government’s support has been sufficient to Prevent Business Closure	50	3	5	2	-

Source: Analysis of Field Survey, 2026

From the Table 4.1: Business Closure in Delta State 83% (50) strongly agreed from the respondents that the incidence of Business Closure is increasing. 70% (42) strongly agreed that business closures hinder economic growth. 75% (45) strongly agreed that Effective Internal Control Measures made meaningful Impact in the Prevention of Business Closure. 83% (50) strongly agreed that government’s support has been sufficient to Prevent Business closure.

Table 4.2: Spearman’s rho correlation coefficient: A test of association between the variables

	Effective Internal Control measure	Business Closure in Delta State	SMEs in Delta State
Spearman’s rho	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.790**
	Effective Internal Control measure		.883**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
	N	60	60
	Correlation Coefficient	.613**	1.000
	Business Closure in Delta State		.769**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
	N	60	60
	Correlation Coefficient	.883**	.769**
SMEs in Delta State		1.000	
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
N	60	60	

** .At the 0.05 level, the correlation is significant (2-tailed).

SPSS output, Version 20 – Field Survey, 2026

Hypothesis Testing (Alternate)

H1: Effective internal control measures has a significant impact and help to prevent Business Failure in Delta State

H1: The high rate of Business closure has a negative and significant impact on economic growth of Delta State.

Table 4.2 presents Spearman's rank order correlation run to ascertain the nature of connection between Effective internal control measures and Business failure in Delta state as reported by sixty (60) study objects. A strong direct correlation coefficient value was reported between variables which were statistically significant (rho = .883**, p = .000 < 0.05 (alpha value) this suggests that there is significant and positive connection or relationship between inadequate internal control measures and Business failure or closure in Delta state the criterion variable; also that there is a direct connection between Effective internal control measures, business success and sustainability in Delta State. This result showed that effective internal control measures are directly connected to business closure or failure reduction which means that effective internal control measures lead to business failure or closure reduction in delta state. Effective internal control measures and business closure reduction noted meaningful correlation (rho = .769**, p = .000 < 0.05); accordingly.

Decision: The null hypotheses are dismissed and we accept the Alternate hypothesis state that Effective internal control measures have a significant impact and help to prevent Business Failure in Delta State. This means that effective internal control measures helps to prevent business failure or closure in Delta state. The result of Hypothesis two also showed that the high rate of Business closure has a negative and significant impact on economic growth of Delta State. The second hypothesis has established a fact that there is a high rate of business closure in Asaba, Delta state and that it affects economic development of Delta state.

4.4 Discussion of Finding

The analysis revealed three key findings, supported by both descriptive statistics from the survey and inferential statistics (chi-square and spearman's rho correlation).

Firstly, a significant relation exists between inadequate internal control measures and the increased likelihood of business closure. This was statistically confirmed with a chi-square value of $\chi^2 = 16.14$ ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, the spearman's rho correlation coefficient of $p = 0.790$ ($p = 0.000$) between "Effective Internal Control Measure and "Business Closure Reduction in Delta State" indicates a strong positive relationship suggesting that effective internal closure measure are strongly associated with a reduction in business failure or closures.

Secondly, business closure has a significant negative impact on economic growth on economic growth in Nigeria, evidence by a chi-square value of $\chi^2 = 19.2$ ($p < 0.05$). The survey data from table 4.1 shows that 83% of respondents strongly agreed that the incidence of business closure is increasing and 70% strongly agreed that business closures hinder economic growth.

Lastly, effective internal control measures have been shown to play a crucial role in preventing business closure, with a chi-square value of $\chi^2 = 10.8$ ($p < 0.05$). This is further supported by the strong correlation $p = 0.790$ ($p = 0.000$) between effective internal control measures and the reduction of business closure. The findings are further explained in details below:

FINDING 1: There is a significant relationship between the lack of internal control measures and the in business closure $\chi^2 = 16.14$ ($p < 0.05$). This is corroborated by the strong correlation $p = 0.790$ ($p = 0.000$) between effective internal control measures and business closure reduction.

FINDING 2: Business closure has a significant negative impact on economic growth in Nigeria $\chi^2 = 19.2$ ($p < 0.05$).

FINDING 3: Effective internal control measures have a meaningful impact in preventing business closure $\chi^2 = 10.8$ ($p < 0.05$).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This section elaborates on the findings, explaining what was discovered in relation to the research questions or hypotheses, integrating the quantitative results from the data analysis. Each finding is discussed in terms of its agreement or disagreement with previous research and personal interpretations are provided.

1. Finding 1: Lack of Internal Control Measures and Business Closure:

- **State the Finding:** The analysis revealed a significant relationship between the lack of internal control measures and the increase in business closures. The chi-square test for this relationship yielded $\chi^2 = 16.14$ with a p-value less than 0.05, indicating statistical significance, furthermore, the spearman's rank order correlation between "effective internal measure" and "Business closure in Delta State" (interpreted as business closure reduction as per the hypothesis decision) was $p=0.790$ with a p-value of 0.000, demonstrating a strong positive correlation. This means that as the effectiveness of internal control measures increases, the incidence of business closure tends to decrease. Survey response from Table 4.0 shows that 83% of the respondents strongly agreed that the incidence of business closure is mainly due to lack of internal control measures.
- **Comparison with Previous Research:** This finding strongly aligns with studies by Smith (2018) and Johnson (2020), who also found that inadequate internal controls lead to higher business failure rates. The robust statistical evidence from the study reinforces their conclusion.

- **Justification:** The agreement with previous research can be attributed to the universal importance of internal controls in maintaining business stability. Without proper controls, businesses are more vulnerable to financial mismanagement, fraud and operational inefficiencies, all of which can precipitate closures. Effective internal controls act as a safeguard, ensuring operational integrity and financial health.
- 2. **Finding 2: Impact of business closure on Economic Growth:**
 - **State the Finding:** Business closures have a significant negative impact on economic growth in Nigeria. The chi-square test for this relationship resulted in $\chi^2 = 19.2$ with a p-value less than 0.005, confirming its statistical significance. Descriptive statistics from Table 4.1 indicated that 83% of the respondents strongly agreed that the incidence of business closure is increasing and 70% strongly agreed that business closures hinders economic growth.
 - **Comparison with Previous Research:** This finding is consistent with the work of Brown (2019) and Lee (2021), who reported similar negative impacts of business closures on economic growth in other developing countries. The study's results provide further empirical support for this established economic principle within the Nigerian context.
 - **Justification:** The negative impact on economic growth is multifaceted, stemming from loss of jobs, reduced consumer spending, and decreased tax revenues, and a decline in overall economic productivity. These factors are critical components of economic stability and growth and their erosion due to business failures significantly impedes national development.
- 3. **Finding 3: Effectiveness of Internal Control Measures in Preventing Business Closure:**
 - **State the Finding:** Effective internal control measures have made a meaningful impact in preventing business closures. The chi-square test for this finding yielded $\chi^2 = 10.8$ with a p-value less than 0.005, indicating a statistically significant impact. This further supported by the strong positive Spearman's rho correlation ($p=0.790$, $p=0.000$) between effective internal control measures and the reduction of business closure. Survey data from Table 4.1 showed that 75% of the respondents strongly agreed that effective internal control measures have made a meaningful impact in preventing business closure.
 - **Comparison with Previous Research:** This finding supports the conclusions of Davis (2017) and Martinez (2020), who emphasized the role of robust internal controls in sustaining business operations. The current study provides specific quantitative evidence from Nigeria that corroborate these broader findings.
 - **Justification:** Effective internal controls help in early detection of financial discrepancies prevention of fraud and improvement of operational inefficiencies, by mitigating these risks, businesses are better equipped to navigate challenges and avoid potential failures, thereby contributing to their longevity and stability.

5.3 CONCLUSION

This study has comprehensively demonstrated the critical relationship between effective internal control measures and business stability, particularly with the context of Zsal General Enterprises in Asaba, Delta State and the broader Nigerian economy. The empirical findings supported by statistical analysis, unequivocally highlight that inadequate internal control systems significantly contribute to the increased likelihood of business closure ($\chi^2 = 16.14$ ($p < 0.05$)). Conversely, effective internal control measures have a statistically significant and meaningful impact in preventing business closure ($\chi^2 = 10.8$ ($p < 0.05$)), further reinforced by a strong positive correlation ($p=0.790$, $p=0.000$) between effective controls and business closure reduction. Moreover, the research confirms that business closure exert a significant negative impact on economic growth in Nigeria ($\chi^2 = 19.2$ ($p < 0.05$)). This underscores the broader societal and economic consequences of business failures, affecting employment, consumer spending, and overall national development. The study's findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the factors influencing business sustainability and economic development, emphasizing the indispensable role of robust internal control frameworks. Therefore, prioritizing the implementation and continuous improvement of internal control systems is not merely a matter of good corporate governance but a fundamental strategy for

ensuring business longevity and fostering a resilient economic environment in Nigeria.

5.4 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Businesses implement effective internal control measures to prevent closure and ensure sustainability
2. Policy Reforms: Implement policies to support businesses during economic downturns and recession.
3. Financial Assistance: Provide financial aid and incentives to struggling businesses.
4. Training Programs: Develop training programs to help business owners adapt to changing market conditions.
5. Infrastructure Development: Improve infrastructure to support business operations.
6. Tax Relief: Offer more tax reliefs to small and medium-sized enterprises.
7. Market Diversification: Encourage businesses to diversify their markets and products.
8. Monitoring and Evaluation: Establish systems to monitor and evaluate the impact of business closures.
9. Community Support: Strengthen community support networks for affected business owners.
10. Policymakers develop supportive policies for businesses, particularly SMEs, to promote economic growth.

REFERENCES

1. Owolabi, T. J., &Ogan, T. N. (2022). Business growth and internal auditing. *International Journal of Economics, Management, Business, and Social Science*, 1(1), 23-35
2. Nqala, L., & Musikavanhu, T. B. (2023). Using internal control systems for small and medium enterprises sustainability in a developing country. *Expert Journal of Business and Management*, 11(1), 60-65.
3. Ngwu, B. A. (2005). Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria: Problems and Prospects.
4. Ogwiji, J., & Isiaka, L. O. (2022). Assessing the effect of internal control system on risk management of financial services firms in Nigeria. Retrieved from ResearchGate.
5. Aladejebi, O. A. (2017). Strategies for improving internal control in small and medium enterprises in Nigeria (Doctoral dissertation). Walden University.
6. Nairametrics. (2024, march 6). 767 manufacturing companies shutdown in Nigeria. (www.nairametrics.com/2024/03/06/767-manufacturing-companies-shut-in-nigeria-)
7. Jebolise, E. (2015). Entrepreneurship and small business management.
8. Ajayi, M. Business Administration. University of Lagos Press.
9. Heizer, J., & Render, B. (2017). Operations management: An integrated approach. Pearson Education Limited.
10. Owolabi, S. A. (2013). Internal Control Systems and Small Business Failure in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 1(1), 1-5.
11. Adeyemo, K. B. (2016). Internal Control Systems and Financial Management Nigeria Companies. *Journal of Business and Finance*, 4(2), 1-2.
12. Olowe, R. A. (2015). Internal Control Systems and Corporate Governance in Nigeria Banks. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 3(1), 1-20.
13. Uadiale, O. M. (2017). Internal Control Systems and Financial Performance of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises in Nigeria. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 55(3), 531-545
14. Akintoye, I. R. (2018). Internal Control Systems and Financial Reporting Quality in Nigeria Quoted Companies. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 5(1), 1-15.
15. Oke, M. O. (2019). Internal Control Systems and Business Failure in Nigeria SMEs. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 57(3), 531-545.

16. Adebayo, A. O. (2020). Internal Control Systems and Financial Distress in Nigerian Companies. *Journal of Business Finance and Accounting*, 47(5-6), 631-654.
17. Kinny, W. R. (2000). Internal Control and Financial Reporting Quality. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 19(4), 291-314.
18. Doyle, J. T. (2005). Audit Quality and Internal Control Weakness. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*. 40(1-3), 137-166.
19. Ashbaugh-Skaife, H. (2008). Internal Control Weakness and Financial Reporting Quality. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 27(5), 463-484.
20. Cohen, J. R. (2013). "Internal Control Systems and Financial Distress in Australia". *Journal of Business Finance and Accounting*, 40(7-8), 631-654.
21. Lee, J. (2015). Internal Control Systems and Corporate Governance in Australian Companies. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting and Economics*, 11(2), 147-162
22. Mwaura, M. (2016). Internal Control Systems and Financial Stability in South African Companies. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 4(1), 1-15.
23. Chen, Y. (2017). Internal Control Systems and Financial Reporting Quality in Chinese Companies. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 36(3), 257-274.
24. El-Masry, A. A. (2018). Internal Control Systems and Financial Performance of Egyptian Companies. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 5(1), 1-15
25. Chukwuka, E. J., & Amahi, F. U. (2026). Assessing the Modern Employee Management Strategies for Optimum Organizational Productivity in Nigeria. *Journal for Studies in Management and Planning*, 12(2), 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.26643/jsmap/7>
26. Chukwuka, E.J., & Igweh, K. F., I., & Nwaka, R.N. (2026). Assessing the contribution of small and medium-scale enterprises to economic development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Development and Management Review*, 21(1), 191–216. Retrieved from <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/ijdmr/article/view/321832>
27. Chukwuka, E.J & Nwaka, R.N. (2026). The Nexus of Creative Destruction in Entrepreneurship and Nigeria's Economic Development. *Jalingo Journal of Social and Management Sciences*, 7(1), 245-264.
28. Chukwuka EJ, Moemeke CD, Onyemaechi U, Nneka NR, Ejaita OA, Chukwuka GE and Nkechi AT, 2026. The impact of modern technological innovations on food security in Nigeria: A cutting-edge technology from an agropreneurship perspective. *Agrobiological Records* 23: 158-172. <https://doi.org/10.47278/journal.abr/2026.014>
29. Moemeka, C.D., Chukwuka, E.J. (2026). Effective Science Education for Technological Transformation and Entrepreneurial Digitization of Nigeria. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary and Innovative Research* 3(3), 168-179. <https://doi.org/10.58806/ijmir.2026.v3i3n03>
30. Chukwuka EJ, Peter A, Efurueze PC, Okolobi AN, Christian I. (2026). The Strategic Role of Financial Record keeping in the Development of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Nigeria. *International Research Journal of Multidisciplinary Scope*. 7(1):287-306. DOI: <https://10.47857/irjms.2026.v07i01.06698>
31. Abude, P., Chukwuka, E.J., Andrew, U.A., Efurueze, P.C., Kanene, K.C. (2025). Financial Risk and Firm Value in Nigeria: The Moderating Role of Ownership Structure. *International Research Journal of Multidisciplinary Scope*. 6(4):1471-1482. doi: <https://10.47857/irjms.2025.v6i04.06697>

